

RADx-UP COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy

Looking Forward: Bridging Infrastructures for
Equitable COVID-19 Testing and Vaccinations

Summary Report

November 17 and 18, 2021

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Executive Summary

Purpose of the Evidence Academy

The RADx-UP COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy provides a starting place to jointly discuss these innovative ideas and make change in communities. An Evidence Academy is an engaged conference approach to understand the state-of-the-science, or the current evidence of COVID-19 testing, testing infrastructures, and related factors in the populations most impacted.

The RADx-UP COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy 2021 - Looking Forward: Bridging Infrastructure for Equitable COVID-19 Testing and Vaccinations was the second Equity Evidence Academy event hosted by the Rapid Acceleration in Diagnostics-Underserved Population (RADx-UP) initiative.

“It is really all about intention,” said Kendrick E. Curry, PhD, MDiv, Pennsylvania Avenue Baptist Church Senior Pastor. Curry delivered the closing keynote at the second RADx-UP **COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy 2021: Looking Forward: Bridging Infrastructures for Equitable COVID-19 Testing and Vaccination**. Curry stressed ‘intention’ as the most crucial ingredient to our success. If we set out with the intention to harness our collective energy and talents we can address not only the COVID-19 pandemic, but the community-level health challenges that existed before the pandemic. His message resounded throughout the two-day event and called for community partners and researchers to critically evaluate how they engage with this work, change it for the better, and collaborate with others to bridge resources, improvise solutions, and challenge the status quo.

This year’s Evidence Academy, hosted by the National Institutes of Health (NIH)-supported Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics-Underserved Populations (RADx-UP), brought together 242 researchers and community and governmental leaders to share their experiences, ideas, and recommendations to bridge best practices and ideas in COVID-19 testing and vaccination across the nation. RADx-UP consists of over 120 funded projects aiming to ensure that all Americans have access to rapid, accurate diagnostics for COVID-19, with a specific focus on populations disproportionately affected by the pandemic. These projects extend across racial and ethnic populations, health-related factors, and settings, and include partnerships with

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academic institutions, community organizations, faith-based organizations, public health agencies, Tribal nations, and other nonprofit organizations.

The 2-day event, held November 17th and 18th 2021, focused on six cross-cutting themes in COVID-19 testing:

THEME 1
**Surge and
Routine Testing**

THEME 4
**Pandemic
Preparedness**

THEME 2
**Data Sharing
Equity**

THEME 5
**Addressing Testing and
Vaccine Policies Big and Small**

THEME 3
**Establishing Communications
Framework**

THEME 6
**Strengthening Multi-Sector
Partnerships**

On the first day of the event, keynote speaker Linda Burhansstipanov, MSPH, PhD, the founder of the Society for Advancement of Chicanos/Hispanics and Native Americans in Science, touched on all six themes within the specific context of American Indian communities. She related both the challenges American Indian communities face and the solutions and wisdom they offer the entire nation. When working with American Indian/Alaska Native communities, she advised that research should begin with the intention to benefit the community, not just researchers. To accomplish this, researchers should strive to work closely with Tribal elders to conduct and share research results. “Most nations feel they have been over-studied with very little benefits to the local community. They say ‘we’ve been surveyed to death and no one shares the results.’ ”

Patti Brennan, RN, PhD, Director, National Library of Medicine delivered the closing keynote address for the first day. She explained how COVID-19 has changed the research agenda by growing new partnerships and reaching new communities. “Research done in Bethesda doesn’t necessarily reach into the lives of everyday people,” she said, emphasizing that the

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NIH is now intentionally investing in community partnerships, specifically those that help bridge data collection, making data more useful for both researchers and communities seeking to improve health. Data collected through effective deployment of technology are already yielding important insights. These data collection methods include home testing strips, smart phone notification systems that inform people about COVID-19 exposure in an anonymous fashion, and culturally respectful, in-the-moment data collection techniques that inform participants about the uses of their data. Brennan also discussed new approaches to research design and communication, and the importance of quickly delivering data about COVID-19 to the community.

On the second day, Marcella Nunez-Smith, MD, MHS, C.N.H Yale University Professor, White House COVID-19 Response Team Senior Advisor, and COVID-19 Health Equity Task Force Chair discussed the federal response to COVID-19. She explained how the COVID-19 Health Equity Task Force works and the recommendations and frameworks for accountability that the Task Force has already created. Nunez-Smith said that from day one, health equity was not just a part of the COVID-19 response, it was, and is, at the center of the response. “This is not a talking point; this is a call to action for this administration.” She thanked RADx-UP community partners for their efforts in the pandemic response and said that researchers and policy makers need to frame all of their efforts around partners and their leadership. “Equity is always going to be hyper-local,” she said.

Across all speakers, breakout sessions, and roundtable discussions, common themes emerged about bridging infrastructures and working with intention to serve communities hardest hit by the pandemic. Participants shared many common experiences and recommendations.

Many participants emphasized **the need for continuous community partnerships**. To truly be prepared for future pandemics or to strengthen multi-sector partnerships, relationships need to be nurtured over time, not just when there is a research need or emergency. Earning the trust needed to advance health requires consistent and long-term partnership in communities. Participants and speakers throughout the Evidence Academy also emphasized many of the principles of community engagement, including the importance of transparency, listening to community wisdom, respect for cultural timelines, and empowering community partners at every step of the research process.

Participants also emphasized **the need to address misinformation**

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compassionately. We are all susceptible to misinformation and it is important to respond to misinformation with compassion and clear, honest messaging. Participants also stressed that messaging should be co-developed with the community and delivered by trusted messengers. To combat misinformation, messages must include the “how and why” context. Educational efforts must also consider health literacy and cultural humility.

Finally, researchers and policy makers need to demonstrate **flexibility in testing initiatives and data collection.** Community-centered research takes community needs and preferences into consideration. Involving the community in study design ensures that the data collected is relevant and easily accessible. Researchers and policy makers should remember that not all communities have the same needs or resources—flexibility with testing and data collection efforts is important. For example, communities may want to co-locate COVID-19 testing with other needed clinical or social services, or use collected data for their own planning and advocacy.

In this report, which is a companion to the [Looking Forward: Bridging Infrastructures for Equitable COVID-19 Testing and Vaccinations Data Profile](#), you will find more information about attendees, the six-cross cutting themes of the event, a summary of keynote presentations, takeaway insights and recommendations from breakout sessions, illustrations from the event, and our lessons learned.

We are thankful to all who participated in our Equity Evidence Academy series and have shared their experiences, their ideas, and their commitment to finding durable, long-term solutions to eliminate health disparities in our nation.

Attendee Demographics/ Characteristics

Attendee Overview—Attendance and Project Affiliation

Gathered from Scarritt Group's registration data

NUMBER OF ATTENDEES

ATTENDEE PROJECT AFFILIATION

Attendee Overview—Race, Gender, and Ethnicity

Gathered from Scarritt Group's registration data

GENDER

ETHNICITY

RACE

Note: 73 people did not report race; 73 people did not report ethnicity; 66 people did not report gender

DAY ONE

Day One included two keynote presentations to launch the Evidence Academy, and centered the attendees on the event's themes from a national perspective. As part of the Evidence Academy, A Visual Approach, LLC created three comprehensive illustrations that reflected the live keynotes and breakout sessions, visually depicting the content discussed.

KEYNOTE ONE

Long-term policies and trust are key to collaborative research with Native American communities

Linda Burnhansstipanov, MSPH, PhD

Linda Burnhansstipanov, MSPH, PhD, founder of the Native American Cancer Research Center, and the opening Evidence Academy keynote speaker is a member of the Cherokee Nation. Burnhansstipanov highlighted the infrastructure needs and best practices for collaborative research with Native American Communities.

Burnhansstipanov opened her keynote with a reminder of the challenges Native Americans face during the COVID-19 pandemic. Native Americans are at higher risk for death and hospitalization from COVID-19 because of a lack of community infrastructure. Additionally, many Tribal reservations lack intensive care beds and ventilators as well as necessities such as quality plumbing, electricity, internet access, and cell phone service. Burnhansstipanov called for federal and state policy changes to provide long-term resources for these communities during COVID-19 and for future public health crises.

She also emphasized the need for respect and understanding of Native American culture. “Trust is the foundation of such policies and support,” Burnhansstipanov explained. Tribal elders and traditional health experts should be involved in all levels of decision-making. They should also be involved in research and data collection. Researchers should identify mutually beneficial ways to study Native American communities. This research should also be representative of Native people as a distinct racial group.

Community-based participatory research is most effective when long-term efforts are made. Burnhansstipanov closed her presentation by explaining that cultural understanding is a lifelong process.

KEYNOTE TWO

Improving Science During the NIH Response to the COVID-19 Pandemic

Patricia Brennan, PhD, RN

Patricia Brennan, PhD, RN, the Director of the National Library of Medicine (NLB), the international resource hub for medical science, provided insight into the many ways the pandemic has changed the nature of research across the NIH and the challenges to engaging communities and individuals in research, while also protecting privacy and making research reproducible and rigorous.

The COVID-19 pandemic has changed the nature of research across the entire NIH. Brennan shared advances in research design, data standards, the application of informatics, and in the accessibility of data analytics.

“We have much more attention to data than ever before,” said Brennan. “Now we’re learning that we need to put the data in new places and use it in new ways.”

Brennan pointed out that these innovations are not without challenges. In order to have research move at the “speed of the pandemic,” the science must be rigorous and reproducible while accounting for diversity amongst communities. She described Common Data Elements (CDEs) as essential to this work and to studying the “phenomena of interest.”

She explained that research must find “the sweet spot” between what is needed by the researcher, the individual, and the science. CDEs must be generalizable enough to recognize commonalities, but also account for diversity in communities and the human experience. CDEs must also be able to capture things that vary between research projects: different people, communities, tests, health systems.

SUMMARY OF KEYNOTE PRESENTATIONS: DAY ONE

Brennan provided examples of new technologies that are advancing the ability to collect data, improve consent forms, and improve data sharing through informatics. However, researchers should consider the unique needs of communities, as some may be left out by these technologies. During the pandemic, the NIH has learned that community-engagement is essential, and should be continuous and ongoing, rather than bounded by a research project. The NIH is addressing this need by creating platforms for community and patient input in the research process.

DAY TWO

KEYNOTE THREE

Q&A with Dr. Marcella Nunez-Smith

Marcella Nunez-Smith MD, MHS

Marcella Nunez-Smith MD, MHS, is the Senior Advisor for the White House COVID-19 Response Team, a chair of the COVID-19 Health Equity Task Force, and a professor at Yale University. The second day of the RADx-UP Equity Evidence Academy opened with an interview with Nunez-Smith. She discussed the path to sustainable and equitable COVID-19 testing and vaccination.

In a Q&A with Lori Carter-Edwards, Nunez-Smith responded to questions about the White House COVID-19 Response Team and how the Biden administration will address social determinants of health in the COVID-19 pandemic.

“We’re trying our best to disrupt the predictability of who is harmed first and harmed worst in times of national crisis,” said Nunez-Smith. One of the goals of the White House COVID-19 Response Team is to “protect those most at risk, and advance equity, including across racial, ethnic, and rural/urban lines.”

She explained that the White House COVID-19 Response Team has made over 300 recommendations for advancing equity to President Biden. Nunez-Smith emphasized that support and partnership with community-based organizations is key to long-lasting solutions and policy for COVID-19 testing and vaccination. Trust is the foundation of relationships with community-based organizations. Nunez-Smith acknowledged that the U.S. government has not always been a trustworthy actor, which is why partnerships with community-based organizations should be hyper-local. Community members should be met where they are. If they can’t be easily met, community organizations and local government should address barriers in the way.

Nunez-Smith concluded the interview with advice for collaboration between researchers, communities, and the government. She emphasized that all learning starts with sharing ideas: She encouraged Evidence Academy participants to be bold, fearless, and honest in the sharing of ideas.

KEYNOTE FOUR

Remarks from Reverend Dr. Kendrick Curry

Kendrick Curry, PhD, MDiv

Kendrick Curry, PhD, MDiv, senior pastor of the Pennsylvania Avenue Baptist Church in Washington, D.C., delivered the final keynote speech on day two of the RADx-UP COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy.

Rev. Curry concluded the Evidence Academy with a speech that highlighted the importance of mindset and intention behind the research. Curry recounted how his church has served its community throughout the COVID-19 pandemic and how serving with intention can build productive partnerships and solutions for addressing the effects of COVID-19 in communities that have been disproportionately impacted by the pandemic.

Intention, explained Curry, is the strong purpose or aim accompanied by determination to produce a desired result. “It’s the force that inspires one to accomplish something great for the greater human good,” he said.

Curry outlined his own experience serving his community through his church, which is one of three ongoing COVID-19 vaccination sites in Washington, D.C. He described the importance of building trusting relationships with community members to best support them. For example, Curry’s congregation hosted webinars and roundtable discussions to educate community members about COVID-19 testing and vaccination, especially those who were hesitant about the topic. Curry also described a street-side vaccination outreach program, where members of the congregation met the community in their daily lives to provide education and resources about COVID-19. Building these connections with the intention to both teach and learn made the outreach successful, he said. Curry closed his address with a recitation of a poem about perseverance by Edgar Albert Guest titled [“It Couldn’t Be Done.”](#)

Definitions and Summaries of Six Cross-Cutting Themes

THEME 1

COVID 19 Surge and Routine Testing

Factors related to ongoing COVID-19 testing in communities. Topics include: testing strategies in communities most impacted, accessible approaches to contact tracing, and testing protocols in schools.

THEME 2

Data Sharing Equity

Sharing health data so researchers can more quickly ask and answer clinical research and public health planning and response questions. Topics include: addressing health disparities with data, improving data infrastructure, reporting and documentation, data sovereignty and other ethical and legal considerations.

THEME 3

Establishing Communication Frameworks

Plans that facilitate bidirectional communication between community members, government officials, and academics can help guide research and policy. Topics include: community and culturally-specific considerations, virtual and non-virtual communications strategies, trusted messengers, addressing misinformation and mistrust in communities.

THEME 4

Pandemic Preparedness

Crafting coordinated response strategies to provide COVID-19 guidance to local health leaders, Tribal nations, and public health organizations and officials. Topics include: health system preparedness, the possibilities and challenges of telehealth, health workforce considerations, national disease surveillance, ensuring equitable testing and vaccine access, flexible federal and local policies.

THEME 5

Addressing Testing and Vaccine Policies Big and Small

The policies that direct testing, screening, and vaccination strategies at the organizational, local and federal levels. Topics include: ensuring accessibility with drive-through, walk-up, or mobile clinic testing sites, developing flexible testing and contact tracing protocols.

THEME 6

Strengthening Multi-Sector Partnerships

Strengthening partnerships across private, academic, and community sectors to support community health and resiliency. Topics include: successful public-private partnerships, the role of healthcare systems and other employers, building long-term community-engaged relationships, encouraging bidirectional knowledge exchange.

Summary of Session Themes

GRAPHIC RECORDING BY A VISUAL APPROACH

• NOVEMBER 17-18, 2021 • 2ND COVID-19 EQUITY EVIDENCE ACADEMY (EA-2) •

Insights and Recommendations from Session Themes

THEME 1 Surge & Routine Testing

- Working with experts to interpret and analyze data and sharing the findings with all stakeholders is essential to identifying patterns in outbreaks of COVID-19, identifying where to allocate resources, and not overlooking marginalized populations.
- Providing consistent, frequent, culturally and linguistically appropriate messaging to all stakeholders about COVID-19 testing is essential to reduce misinformation and encourage testing amongst marginalized populations.
- Starting early in the pandemic, researchers and public health agencies have relied on non-traditional community organizations as partners to disseminate messages about testing and establish pop-up testing sites that are accessible. Clinics did not necessarily have the capacity or the trust of marginalized populations to be the only testing sites.
- There are pros and cons to pop-up testing locations:

Pros include:

- Community-based organizations (CBOs) may have locations that are more accessible to community members than a traditional clinic. Clinics were not resourced for testing in early phases of the pandemic.
- CBOs have established trust and built relationships with communities.
- CBOs can provide other needed services alongside COVID-19 testing and messaging.

Cons include:

- Difficulty to staff and resource in a sustainable way.
- Burden on the CBOs and other volunteers who have competing responsibilities.
- Lack of sustainable revenue and/or funding to continue over the long term.
- Lack of resources to address positive test results.

INSIGHTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FROM SESSION THEMES

- To increase sustainability, it is important to establish revenue streams for compensating labs and community organizations for their roles in COVID-19 testing.
- When working with CBOs such as schools, programs must be turnkey since there are many services that these organizations are responsible for providing.
- Now that testing is more widely available, next steps may include returning testing to clinical settings while continuing to support nontraditional partners' efforts to create sustainable revenue streams and infrastructure for continuing COVID-19 related services.
- In rural communities, for-profit healthcare organizations may not have the revenue to sustain testing programs. Federal dollars should be allocated to support testing in rural areas.
- Public health organizations and healthcare organizations should continue to break silos. When addressing COVID-19 testing, partnership and collaboration can support addressing the social determinants of health and many contributing social and health-related factors for communities and individuals.
- Now that testing is widely available, healthcare providers and public health agencies can encourage testing before large gatherings, such as holiday celebrations. The accessibility of free in-home testing provides more opportunities to community members who may prefer that option.

THEME 2 Data Sharing Equity

- Data inequity is structural and historical, tracing back to how data has traditionally been collected in the United States starting in the 1700's. This has led to a systematic erasure of some minority communities in our country.
- Aggregation of data pertaining to minority populations doesn't tell the whole story and should not be taken at face value. It can generate misleading conclusions about the health of minority populations, which means we are conducting and publishing research and making public health decisions based on just a portion of the population.
- Relying on aggregated data for making policy decisions, allocating resources, and planning health interventions can be harmful to the most vulnerable populations who aren't represented in the data.
- We cannot default to categorizing groups into the "other"/ "missing" category under the guise of protecting those with small numbers. Strategies exist to collect and present data and still protect individuals' privacy.
- Having community specific data allows for tailored interventions and partnering with trusted community members and organizations can help use data to tailor engagement strategies and deliver COVID-19 education, prevention, healthcare, and vaccination efforts.
- Disaggregation of data by race/ethnicity and consideration of racial and ethnic sub-groups is key to reducing health inequities, understanding health disparities, driving resource allocation, and designing culturally tailored public health interventions and policy-decisions.
- Due to long-standing methods of data collection, researchers cannot always change the way data is collected, such as when conducting a secondary data analysis. However, researchers can contextualize the analysis to the communities they are working with by considering diversity and cultural factors as well as the communities' history and their needs.
- Partnering with CBOs and consulting community stakeholders and organizations in the data collection process, and when planning and implementing public health interventions, is critical in minority cultures.
- The design phase of Common Data Elements (CDEs) and data collection instruments should not be rushed. Time and effort should be taken to include communities' input early to ensure cultural relevancy of CDEs to the diverse communities the RADx-UP project teams are engaging in their work.
- NIH should be proactive in sharing data across and within communities. Pathways should be created for resource-rich communities to share knowledge with low-resource communities.

THEME 3

Establishing Communications Frameworks

- To provide the populations engaged in the research process with timely, necessary resources, research teams should consider partnering with community health workers who have pre-existing relationships with other CBOs and community members.
- Establishing a communications framework requires not only establishing partnerships with trusted community individuals and organizations—research teams must also ensure that the information is relevant, relatable, and applicable to the community being served.
- Research teams may improve their communication and relations with communities they wish to engage by considering individual communities' historical and cultural sentiments towards healthcare and modern medicine and by embracing any pre-existing traditional and holistic practices that are culturally relevant.
- In order to reduce language barriers, communicators should advocate for access to, and production of, more inclusive state and federal materials, invest in interpreters, and involve community partners in the creation of communications materials.
- An individual's perception and reception of messages about COVID-19 may be influenced by their recent engagement with emergent infectious diseases, misleading comparisons to other infectious diseases, and/or the mode in which they received the information.
- Under certain circumstances we are all vulnerable to misinformation, and therefore it is important to have empathy when framing messages intended to dispel it. There may be emotional and social context driving people to believe messaging contrary to the current science.

THEME 4 Pandemic Preparedness

- To bring about effective community change, research teams should consider the following steps:
 - Identify issues that community members are facing by holding small focus groups and forums with diverse stakeholders;
 - Determine plans for action by involving the community in discussions about their needs and thoughts surrounding a pandemic;
 - Compare data between communities to identify trends and inform action steps, which may aid in establishing systems that better prepare the community for future pandemics;
 - Reflect on successes and challenges of past plans and use this process to inform future initiatives;
 - Report lessons learned to the community to keep individuals informed and give them an active role in their community's pandemic preparedness planning.
 - Pathways are needed for individuals—particularly youth—to be more engaged. One example is community advisory boards, which can result in them getting more involved in the research and for them to learn more about research.
 - For example, creating curriculum to report findings; understand how funding works, and becoming PIs themselves in the future.
- Communication strategies are needed to inform the population and counter misinformation and/or disinformation. Additionally, it is important to try to understand and address the mental health impacts of a pandemic.
- Engaging trusted networks can help organizations identify community partners and frameworks that are already in place. By partnering with trusted community partners and established communication channels, individuals are more likely to feel that they are being worked with and not on.
- Collaboration between multiple community and state organizations helps bring together resources and expertise from varying backgrounds.
- When you have a system in place, it is easier to respond to future pandemics and other public health emergencies.

INSIGHTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FROM SESSION THEMES

- When developing public health emergency preparedness plans, a good legal framework should be established that includes current legal mandates, legal implications of the work, and definitions of where organizational, state and any other stakeholders' legal authority begins and ends.
- Emergency preparedness planning efforts must keep equity at the forefront to ensure equitable access to accurate, relevant, and timely information for all members of a community.
- While going through a pandemic such as COVID-19, remembering that individuals still need regularly provided services is important. Providing other needed services such as food distribution, job fairs, school registration, etc. alongside vaccinations and/or testing makes vaccinations and testing more easily accessible to community members in need.
- The pandemic has had an effect on other aspects of an individual's well-being such as their mental health. Access to services to address these needs should be considered in planning efforts for future pandemics.
- When framing messaging about the most current evidence surrounding COVID-19, it is important to acknowledge that science itself leads to changing information and there is a significant amount of potential for error. The current evidence may become false over time and depending on the context, become misinformation, which is misleading and deceptive.
- Individuals can combat misinformation for themselves and positively impact others in their sphere of influence to do the same by being open about the science surrounding COVID-19, being aware of the misinformation circulating, providing credible resources and materials about COVID-19 to individuals, and empowering others to seek out information on their own.
- Technological barriers to receiving and disseminating information about COVID-19 can be combated by increasing the accessibility and affordability of technology, advocating for better internet access in remote and rural areas, and training individuals on how to use various technological platforms and devices.

THEME 5

Addressing Testing and Vaccine Policies Big and Small

- American Indian /Alaska Native (AI/AN), Native Hawaiian, and Pacific Islander communities may have mistrust for government and healthcare as a result of numerous historical traumas including previous pandemics, denial of access to health resources, forced sterilizations, and broken treaties and agreements with governments. Therefore, to develop strong policies within these communities, there must be involvement from trusted partners who have longstanding relationships with community members.
- AI/AN Tribal communities are diverse and therefore so are their needs related to the management of COVID-19. Testing needs to be adaptable and accessible to individuals from a wide variety of backgrounds to successfully track and contain COVID-19.
- Similarly, community education around testing should be accessible in a variety of formats at a level that can be easily understood.
- Outcomes are easier to achieve when organizational goals and values align, and it is important to clarify deliverables and responsibilities when entering contractual partnerships between organizations. Flexibility is necessary, particularly with the changing needs of the pandemic
- In communities with historic mistrust of US health policies, repeating health messages multiple times and in a variety of formats may be particularly necessary as trust is being built. Trust can be developed within a community through consistency, clear parameters, and by providing opportunities for comments and questions.
- Connecting with and educating policymakers is essential to developing safe COVID-19 policies that address communities' needs. An example of a successful policy developed by Chicago Public Schools is the creation of Vaccine Awareness Day. Classes were paused for a full day to allow students the time to get vaccinated.
- Communication gaps remain between policymakers and community partners. Stronger linkages need to be forged to help dispel misinformation. Policies must connect communities to research and address intersectional and comprehensive health needs. Sharing research results is one strategy for building trust.
- In order to form successful COVID-19 policies, it is essential to build coalitions between policymakers, scientists, and people with lived experience. Policy uniformity must be balanced with context-dependent needs.
- Policies should address technology infrastructure and disparities in access. Permanent solutions are needed, not just temporary solutions. Projects with common approaches can benefit from partnering to help pool data and share strategies.

THEME 6

Strengthening Multi-Sector Partnerships

- In order to form successful, sustainable multi-sector partnerships, all parties involved should address gaps in technology and provide equal access to information that is appropriate for all relevant literacy levels. Resources should be allocated based on the community's needs and priorities.
- Community partners must drive decision making both on the research and clinical side of COVID-19 research. Sustainable change comes from infrastructure built directly into communities, rather than support that is funneled through larger institutions.
- In responding to COVID-19, the needs of the community are constantly changing, so response strategies must be easily adaptable.
- COVID-19 should be treated as a syndemic, where health, social, and spiritual needs must be met in both the individual and the group.
- Equity-first based response is necessary to avoid a resurgence in redlining as a result of the pandemic. COVID-19 support services should be provided for a variety of needs, including food, housing, and mental health. To better achieve their intended impact, partnerships must develop “webs of trust” that set up more equitable structures for the future, which requires policy change and partnering with a variety of different sectors. Trusted providers and contingency planning enable advocating for a stronger public health infrastructure. Building trust, familiarity, and comfort are necessary to encourage individuals to accept new things.
- Members of all groups are human beings who should be respected as individuals and not “othered.” Information gained through research should be used to improve the lives of community members and not remain research for research's sake. The correct way to engage community members involves relationship-building, which then develops into engaging in inquiry around the goals and priorities of the group. From there, roles in the work can be defined by the community and then infrastructure is built around the community's identified goals.
- When developing partnerships, it is important to keep the philosophy of “nothing about us without us” in mind. Trusted community leaders are able to communicate information to the community in a way that is more likely to be effective. Faith-based organizations and CBOs have become integral partners in the process of combatting COVID-19.
- In working with communities around COVID-19 mitigation strategies, it has become clear that methodology matters and the needs of the individual should always be accounted for. People have developed preferences around tests and are more likely to seek out and complete a test that they prefer. Above all, it is necessary to listen to people and value their self-reported needs. All sectors can participate in the development of strategies to combat COVID-19 and varied viewpoints are valuable in coming up with robust policies.

Lessons Learned

Rapid advances in COVID-19 testing and vaccination technologies necessitate flexible underlying structures that support equity in services and care, specifically among populations of greatest impact. Over this two-day engaged event, presentations and conversations focused on the varying, multi-level components for building infrastructures to address COVID-19 testing and vaccination in vulnerable communities. As with the first Evidence Academy (EA1) on COVID-19 testing technologies held in February 2021, the themes at this meeting were cross-cutting, complex, and multi-level. We learned that sustainable structural solutions must support communities' capacities to deliver public health services equitably.

We learned that to develop long-term structural solutions, **we need to connect available resources by breaking down silos between organizations and people.** Speakers from different disciplines discussed creating or maintaining partnerships through coordinated planning and implementation to bridge information and ideas. These partnerships are critical in a pandemic where information and resources are rapidly changing.

We also learned that building infrastructure should be addressed using a multi-layered approach. Communication, trustworthiness, and data dissemination were key, cross-cutting themes in both Evidence Academies. They serve as common threads for improving the state of the science as well as the state of the practice in COVID-19 testing and vaccination, and are essential for building effective interventions. **Engaging trusted community organizations early and often** can assist scientists in understanding cultural considerations for messaging, considering historical traumas that may affect community norms, and navigating communications frameworks that are already in place. Often non-traditional partners in healthcare and healthcare research, CBOs, can serve as liaisons between the lay community and the academic healthcare system. The contextual expertise of these CBOs can inform decision making and lead to more efficient processes for access and successful delivery of COVID-19 testing and vaccinations. These trusted sources can translate data shared by scientists into understandable and culturally relevant messages to promote rapid response by community members, particularly those less trusting of the healthcare system. While data may need to be rapidly shared in a pandemic, engaging the community cannot happen rapidly. Engagement should be meaningful, not rushed, and should be threaded throughout each step of the research process. This approach builds the

LESSONS LEARNED

trust necessary for continual data sharing by the scientists and rapid, willing response to this data by communities.

In terms of data, we also learned that **disaggregating data amongst minority groups is imperative to resource allocation and public health planning**. To understand the burden of COVID-19 and other health disparities, scientists must make efforts to move away from traditional data analysis methods of grouping smaller minority populations into 'other' categories. Innovative data collection and secondary analysis methods must be adopted to account for the many cultural nuances and the diversity that exists for many racial and ethnic groups, specifically American Indians, Alaskan Natives, Pacific Islanders, and other populations often marginalized in research.

Finally, we learned that **we need to be intentional in our actions when we conduct engaged research**. The pandemic continues to highlight how different partners come to the table and collectively work to combat COVID-19. Being cognizant of one's purpose as well as one's role in partnered research is the springboard to forming effective collaborations. When we work together to share ideas, address conflict, and generate solutions we are able to minimize and even mitigate structural barriers to health equity.

We hope that the information shared on bridging infrastructures and the connections made during this event promote a new more collaborative approach to addressing COVID-19 testing and vaccination technologies. RADx-UP teams partnering with trusted local leaders to put the community first can lead to positive changes in the public health infrastructure and increased community engagement surrounding COVID-19 and beyond.

Acknowledgments

LEADERSHIP OF THE RADx-UP CDC AND CEAL I-TEAM

RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDC) Co-Principal Investigators

Micky Cohen-Wolkowicz, MD, PhD
Duke Clinical Research Institute

Giselle Corbie, MD, MSc
University of North Carolina (UNC)
Center for Health Equity Research

Warren Kibbe, PhD
Duke University

STEERING COMMITTEE MEMBERS

Sergio Aguilar-Gaxiola, MD, PhD
University of California, Davis

Natalie Bowman, MD
University of North Carolina
at Chapel Hill

Arleen Brown, MD, PhD
University of California, Los Angeles

Dedra Buchwald, MD
Washington State University

Goldie Byrd, PhD
Wake Forest School of Medicine

Paul Chung, MD, MS
Kaiser Permanente Bernard J. Tyson
School of Medicine

Emily Haroz, PhD, MA, MHS
Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School
of Public Health

Nadia Islam, PhD
NYU Langone Health

Edward Kissam
The Werner-Kohnstamm Family
Giving Fund (WKF)

Jay Leggette
The Stimulus

Erica Marsh, MD, MSCI, FACOG
University of Michigan

Viviana Martinez-Bianchi, MD, FAAFP
Duke University

James “Lloyd” Michener, MD
Duke University School of Medicine

Marcella Nunez-Smith, MD, MHS
Yale School of Medicine, White House
COVID-19 Response Team Presidential
COVID-19 Health Equity Task Force

Tina Tauasosi-Posiulai, PhD
University of Hawaii-Manoa

Christopher Woods, MD, PhD
Duke University

DATA PROFILE REVIEWERS AND CONTEXT CONTRIBUTORS

Broderick Crawford
NBC Community Development
Corporation

Ilana Dubester
El Vínculo Hispano

Tinka Duran, MPH
Great Plains Tribal Leaders Health
Board

John Foxe, PhD
University of Rochester Medical Center

May Okihiro, MD
John A. Burns School of Medicine-
University of Hawaii at Manoa

Mary Ricketts
NBC Community Development
Corporation

Ephraim L Tsalik, MD, PhD
Duke University

Karen Zandi
Mary Cariola Center

Anna Zavodszky
Duke-Robert J. Margolis, MD, Center
for Health Policy

Laura Villa Torres, PhD, MSPH
University of North Carolina at Chapel
Hill

Greizy Beckles
Community Reviewer

Mysha Wynn, MA, BA
Community Reviewer

Rubi Franco Quiroz
Community Reviewer

Tony Locklear
Community Reviewer

Xiomara Mathison
Community Reviewer

Kayla Korzekwinski
Duke Clinical Research Institute

Terren Green
Duke Clinical Research Institute

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

DATA PROFILE DEVELOPERS

Heather Wilson

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Sophia Ramirez

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Cassidy Fox, MSW

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Lindsay Bailey, MPH

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Eno Idiagbonya

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Jenny Cook, MPH

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Mary Lindsley

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Zhitong Yu

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Alicia Bilheimer, MPH

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Renee Leverty, MA

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Bukola Adeshina, MPH

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Lori Carter-Edwards, PhD, MPH

Kaiser Permanente Bernard J. Tyson School of Medicine

Data Profile design by

Kerry Stenke

Duke Clinical Research Institute

CORE PLANNING TEAM

Lori Carter-Edwards, PhD, MPH

Kaiser Permanente Bernard J. Tyson School of Medicine

Renee Leverty, MA

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Camille Brown-Lowery, MA

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Bukola Adeshina, MPH

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Alicia Bilheimer, MPH

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Kathleen (Katie) Brandert, MPH

University of Nebraska

Lindsay Bailey, MPH

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Eno Idiagbonya

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Cassidy Fox, MSW

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

FULL PLANNING TEAM

Lori Carter-Edwards, PhD, MPH

Kaiser Permanente Bernard J. Tyson School of Medicine

Giselle Corbie, MD, MSc

University of North Carolina (UNC) Center for Health Equity Research

Lindsay Bailey, MPH

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Eno Idiagbonya

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Cassidy Fox, MSW

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Christina Silcox, PhD

Duke-Margolis Center for Health Policy

Alicia Bilheimer, MPH

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Phillip Horn, MSW, MPH

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Goldie Byrd, PhD

Wake Forest School of Medicine

Krista Perreira, PhD

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Andea Thoumi, MPP, MSc

Duke-Margolis Center for Health Policy

Renee Leverty, MA

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Jennifer Cook, MPH

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Heather Wilson

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Rosa Gonzalez-Guarda, PhD, MPH

Duke University Clinical Translational Science Institute

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Barrie Harper

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Hailey Leiva, MSW

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Jenni Detwiler

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Camille Brown-Lowery, MA

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Crystal Cannon, MA

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Laura Johnson, MHS

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Rachel Quinto

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Mary Lindsley

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Tracey Hawkins, MA

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Miranda Wenhold

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Deepti Baheti, MD

United Medical Center (TX)

Al Richmond, MSW

Community-Campus Partnerships for Health

Bukola Adeshina, MPH

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Maria Cristina Ramos Flor, PhD

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Abisola Osinuga, PhD

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Kathleen (Katie) Brandert, MPH

University of Nebraska

Susan Knox

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Sophia Ramirez

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Helena Pike Welch

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Hannah Marie Potter, MPH

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

KEYNOTE SPEAKERS

Linda Burhansstipanov, MSPH, PhD

Society for Advancement of Chicanos/Hispanics and Native Americans in Science

Patti Brennan, RN, PhD

National Library of Medicine

Marcella Nunez-Smith, MD, MHS

Yale University, White House COVID-19 Response Team, Presidential COVID-19 Health Equity Task Force

Kendrick E. Curry, PhD, MDiv

Pennsylvania Avenue Baptist Church, Black Coalition Against COVID-19

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

BREAKOUT SESSION SPEAKERS

Hakeem Adeniyi, MD

Sacramento Native American
Health Center

Virginia Hedrick, MPH

Consortium for Urban Indian
Health

**Julie Pryde, MPH, MSW, LMSW,
CPHA**

Champaign-Urbana Public Health
District (CUPHD)

Awais Vaid, MD, MPH

Champaign-Urbana Public Health
District (CUPHD)

Abeni Bloodworth

Chromatic Black

Clemens Hong, MD, MPH

Los Angeles County Department
of Health Services (DHS)

Somava Saha, MD, MS

Well-being and Equity in the World
(WE in the World), Well Being In
the Nation (WIN) Network

Stella Yi, MPH, PhD

NYU Grossman School
of Medicine

Irene De Barraicua

Líderes Campesina

Caleb King

Cook Inlet Tribal Council, Inc.

Raynald Samoa, MD

City of Hope Medical Center

Kenneth Fox, MD

Chicago Public Schools

Janice Lucas, MA

LEAD Coalition of Bay County

Becky Smith, PhD, MS, DVM

University of Illinois College of
Veterinary Medicine, Carle-Illinois
College of Medicine

Deliana Garcia, MA

Migrant Clinicians Network

Aziza Lucas-Wright, MEd

The College of Medicine at
Charles R. Drew University of
Medicine and Science (CDU)

Brian Southwell, PhD

Duke University, RTI International

EA2 PLANNING TEAM AND VOLUNTEERS

Ann-Marie Akiwumi, MPH PMP

IMPAQ International

Ahmad Alach

Kaiser Permanente Bernard J.
Tyson School of Medicine

Deepti Baheti, MD

United Medical Center (TX)

Claire Beard

Duke University

Ann Burnette

Duke University Medical Center

Naomi Carbrey, MPH

University of North Carolina at
Chapel Hill

Jennifer Cook, MPH

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Jenni Detwiler

University of North Carolina at
Chapel Hill

Brandy Farrar, MS, PhD

IMPAQ International

Simone Frank, MPH

University of North Carolina at
Chapel Hill

**Rosa Gonzalez-Guarda, PhD,
MPH**

Duke University Clinical
Translational Science Institute

Melissa Green, MPH

UNC Gillings School of Public
Health

MaryBeth Grewe, MPH

University of North Carolina at
Chapel Hill

Anna Gross, MPH

University of North Carolina at
Chapel Hill

Fatima Guerrab, MPH, CHES

University of North Carolina at
Chapel Hill

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Barrie Harper

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Tracey Hawkins, MA

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Lauren Hill, PhD

UNC Gillings School of Public Health

Paula Hornstein

Kaiser Permanente Bernard J. Tyson School of Medicine

Angelique Jennings, MPH

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Cortez M. Johnson, MBA

Kaiser Permanente Bernard J. Tyson School of Medicine

Laura Johnson, MHS

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Tamara Jones

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Kamaria Kaalund

Duke-Margolis Center for Health Policy

Alexa Katon, MS

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Lia Kaz, MSW

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Kelly Keefe, MHA, PMP

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Susan Knox

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Hailey Leiva, MSW

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

May Let Wah

Kaiser Permanente Bernard J. Tyson School of Medicine

Mary Lindsley

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Judithe Louis, MSW, CCTP

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Sydney Lufsey

IMPAQ International

Courtney Mann, MA

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Gretchen Mason, MPH

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Cherry Maynor Beasley, PhD, MS, FNP, RN, CNE, FAAN

The University of North Carolina at Pembroke McKenzie-Elliott School of Nursing

Paula Mian, MPP

IMPAQ International

Alberto Ortega-Hinojosa, PhD, MPH

IMPAQ International

Kaniqua Outlaw, MPH

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Helena Pike Welch

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Hannah Potter, MPH

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Julia Rehder

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Anna L. Richards

Kaiser Permanente Bernard J. Tyson School of Medicine

Catherine Rohweder, DrPH

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Christina Silcox, PhD

Duke-Margolis Center for Health Policy

Amanda Souto, MPH

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Andrea Thoumi, MPP, MSc

Duke-Margolis Center for Health Policy

Laura Villa Torres, PhD, MSPH

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Keiana Watkins, MSPH

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Roger Williams, MA, MPH

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Zhitong Yu

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Anton Zuiker, MA

Duke Clinical Research Institute

Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics-Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) is an initiative of the The National Institutes of Health, in partnership with the Duke Clinical Research Institute and the UNC Center for Health Equity Research. RADx-UP aims to ensure that all Americans have access to COVID-19 testing, with a focus on communities across the country that most affected by the pandemic. The initiative is researching testing patterns, disparities in infection rates, disease progression and outcomes in those communities. It is also developing strategies to reduce disparities in COVID-19 testing by supporting projects across the country with established community partnerships.

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